

A Combinatorial Neutron Transport Solver: Linking Local Neural Surrogates via Interface Currents

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803383

ABSTRACT

Neutron transport calculation is fundamental to reactor design, yet existing methods face significant challenges. Monte Carlo (MC) offers high fidelity but at prohibitive computational cost, while deterministic methods struggle with complex geometries and resonance effects. This study proposes a novel Monte Carlo-Deep Learning-Interface Current (MC-DL-IC) coupling method, establishing a "data generation—pattern learning—physical constraint enforcement" framework. The method employs MC to generate high-fidelity simulation data for a finite set of standardized basic units. Deep Learning (DL) models are then trained to learn the local mapping laws between incident and outgoing angular fluxes for these units. Finally, the Interface Current (IC) method enforces angular flux continuity at unit interfaces during a global sweeping iteration, ensuring physical consistency across complex geometries assembled from the basic units. This approach presents a new paradigm that could potentially redefine the conventional deterministic workflow, shifting from traditional resonance and multi-group transport steps to combinatorial modeling using pre-trained neural network surrogates. Validation results demonstrate excellent agreement with reference MC solutions, with eigenvalue errors below 100 pcm and relative errors in neutron flux density and fission source distributions within 1% for tested assembly problems. The method effectively overcomes the generalization limitations of purely data-driven models while maintaining high accuracy.

Keywords: Monte Carlo; Deep Learning; Interface Current; Neutron Transport; Surrogate Model

1. INTRODUCTION

High-fidelity neutron transport calculations are crucial for nuclear reactor design, directly impacting safety and economics. Achieving both high accuracy and computational efficiency remains challenging with existing approaches. State-of-the-art methods present a clear trade-off: Monte Carlo (MC) methods handle complex geometries and energy spectra but are computationally expensive [1], while deterministic methods are more efficient but face challenges with resonance effects and irregular geometries [2], [3].

Deep learning has emerged as a promising tool, with applications ranging from Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) [4], [5] to enhancing traditional methods [6]. However, these end-to-end models are often problem-specific and struggle with generalization beyond their training domain. Inspired by successes of DL in complex physical systems [7], [8], [9], this work proposes a hybrid approach that leverages the strengths of MC, DL, and deterministic methods.

This paper presents the Monte Carlo-Deep Learning-Interface Current (MC-DL-IC) coupling method. Its core innovation lies in using DL to learn local physics of standard basic units, which are then assembled to solve global problems under physical interface constraints, avoiding the need for problem-specific retraining.

2. METHODOLOGY

The MC-DL-IC method follows a synergistic workflow, illustrated in *Figure 1*.

2.1. Basic Idea and Workflow

The method decomposes the global transport problem into manageable steps:

- 1) **Definition of Basic Units:** A finite library of standardized geometric units (e.g., homogeneous rectangles, heterogeneous pin-cells, triangles) is defined. Each unit is characterized by geometric (P_{geo}) and material (P_{mat}) parameters.
- 2) **Data Generation & Surrogate Model Training:** High-fidelity MC simulations (using NECP-MCX [10]) are performed for each unit type under varied parameters, incident fluxes, and eigenvalues (k_{eff}). This generates datasets mapping inputs to outgoing angular fluxes and fission sources. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) are trained as fast surrogates for this mapping.
- 3) **Combinatorial Problem Construction:** Target problems (e.g., fuel assemblies) are constructed by assembling the basic units. Interface links are established based on adjacency.
- 4) **Global Sweeping Solution:** The interface current method is employed. The pre-trained unit surrogates are linked via angular flux continuity conditions at interfaces. A cell-by-cell sweeping iteration updates incident fluxes and the global eigenvalue until convergence.

Figure 1. Fundamental concept of the MC-DL-IC coupling method.

2.2. Modeling of Basic Units

The core of the MC-DL-IC method lies in utilizing standardized basic units as fundamental building blocks. The methodology accommodates diverse geometric configurations, from simple homogeneous rectangles to complex heterogeneous pin-cells, as illustrated in *Figure 2* and *Figure 3*. These encompass regular triangles, annular sectors, curvilinear triangular units for complex surface modeling, as well as rectangular and hexagonal fuel pin-cell units representing typical reactor structures. The physical response of any basic unit is characterized by a Boundary Response Operator, R , which encapsulates the complex internal neutron transport behavior. For a basic unit containing F surfaces, this operator defines the mapping from incident angular flux on any surface to outgoing angular flux on all surfaces, and optionally the internal fission source, and is formally expressed as:

$$\{\psi_{\text{out}}, q_f\} = R(\psi_{\text{in}}, k, P_{\text{geo}}, P_{\text{mat}}). \quad (1)$$

where ψ_{in} is the incident angular flux, k is the global eigenvalue, and P_{geo} and P_{mat} are the geometric and material parameters, respectively.

The material parameters can be defined either directly via macroscopic cross-sections for methodological studies or through key physical parameters (e.g., enrichment, temperature) for engineering practicality. This parametric characterization allows a finite set of unit types to represent a wide range of physical scenarios.

Figure 2. Schematics of basic geometric units (rectangular, triangular, annular, sector, and curvilinear triangular basic units, respectively).

Figure 3. Schematics of basic pin-cell units (rectangular and hexagonal pin-cells).

2.3. Training of Surrogate Models

High-fidelity datasets for training are generated using the Monte Carlo code NECP-MCX [10]. For each basic unit type, a large number of simulations are performed by sampling different combinations of unit parameters, incident flux distributions, and the global eigenvalue.

A key aspect of data generation for units containing fissile material is the treatment of the eigenvalue k . In the training phase, k is treated as an input parameter to the unit-level fixed-source problem. For each sample, a k value is uniformly sampled within a plausible range (e.g., [0.5, 1.5]). The MC simulation is then run in a fixed-source iteration mode, with the sampled k used to normalize the fission source, simulating the unit's response under that specific eigenvalue. This allows the DNN surrogate to learn the functional relationship $\{\psi_{out}, q_f\} = R(\psi_{in}, k, P_{geo}, P_{mat})$, which is essential for the subsequent global sweeping iteration where the current estimate $k^{(n)}$ is fed into the models.

Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), specifically Fully Connected Networks (FCNs), are then trained to approximate the Boundary Response Operator R . For geometrically simple homogeneous units, a single DNN can directly predict all output quantities. For complex heterogeneous units like pin-cells, we developed a decomposed prediction strategy to master the intricate spatial-angular coupling. This strategy employs specialized sub-networks, each dedicated to predicting a specific aspect of the response: the total outgoing scalar flux, its spatial distribution ratio across surfaces, the angular distribution on each surface, and the fission source term. The final outgoing angular flux is reconstructed by combining these components: $\psi_{out} = \Phi_{total} \times R_{spatial} \times f_{angular}$. This decomposed approach, compared to a single network predicting all outputs simultaneously, achieved lower prediction error (as evidenced by validation MSE in our full study), demonstrating its efficacy in handling strong heterogeneity. This approach yielded high accuracy, with 94.76% of final reconstructed angular flux predictions exhibiting errors below 1.5%, as detailed in Section 3.1.2.

Limitation Note: The current study focuses on demonstrating the feasibility and accuracy of the MC-DL-IC framework. A formal uncertainty quantification (UQ) analysis, encompassing the stochasticity in neural network training and the statistical errors in MC-generated training data, is not presented here but is recognized as an important aspect for future robust deployment. In this work, measures such as early stopping, L2 regularization, and sufficient MC particle histories were employed to enhance the stability and reliability of the surrogate models. Datasets were typically randomly split into 80% for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing.

2.4. Global Sweeping Calculation Scheme

The global solution is achieved through an iterative sweeping scheme based on the interface current method, which physically links the independent unit surrogate models. As illustrated in *Figure 4*, the computational domain, assembled from basic units, undergoes sequential processing in a systematic sweeping pattern. The procedure for the n -th iteration comprises the following steps:

Figure 4. Sweeping calculation scheme for neutron transport.

- 1) Unit-level Calculation: Each unit i is processed sequentially by invoking its corresponding pre-trained surrogate model $f_{\text{dnn},i}$. The model receives the current incident angular fluxes on all surfaces, the global eigenvalue $k^{(n)}$, and unit parameters, then predicts outgoing angular fluxes and the internal fission source $q_{f,i}^{(n)}$.

- 2) Interface Information Transfer: Outgoing angular flux from each unit directly provides the incident angular flux for adjacent neighbor units, rigorously enforcing physical continuity conditions at interfaces.
- 3) Eigenvalue Update: Following complete domain processing, the total fission source is summed and the global eigenvalue is updated to $k^{(n+1)}$ using the power iteration method, maintaining neutron population balance.
- 4) Convergence Check: The iteration continues until the relative changes in both the global eigenvalue and the fission source distribution fall below specified convergence thresholds:

$$\frac{|k^{(n+1)} - k^{(n)}|}{k^{(n+1)}} < \epsilon_k \text{ and } \max_i \frac{\|\mathbf{q}_{f,i}^{(n+1)} - \mathbf{q}_{f,i}^{(n)}\|_2}{\|\mathbf{q}_{f,i}^{(n+1)}\|_2} < \epsilon_q$$

where ϵ_k and ϵ_q are convergence tolerances, typically set to 10^{-5} in this work. If the criteria are met, the calculation terminates; otherwise, it proceeds to the next iteration ($n+1$).

This sweeping scheme dynamically integrates the local surrogate models into a collaborative network, enforcing global physical consistency to obtain the final solution for the assembled problem.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All validations employed a one-group approximation with macroscopic cross-sections.

3.1. Unit-level Model Performance

The surrogate models for basic units demonstrated high accuracy in standalone tests, providing the foundation for global calculations.

3.1.1. Homogeneous Medium Rectangular Unit

For a homogeneous rectangular unit with a side length of 1.26 cm (*Figure 5*), a single Fully Connected Network (FCN) was trained to map the incident angular flux, global eigenvalue, and unit parameters to the outgoing angular fluxes and fission source. The unit was characterized by macroscopic cross-sections of $\Sigma_t = 0.40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Sigma_s = 0.36 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\nu\Sigma_f = 0.04 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 600 K. The optimal network architecture consisted of five hidden layers (128-64-32-16-8 neurons), achieving a remarkably low mean relative deviation of 0.0011% on the prediction set, demonstrating its exceptional accuracy in capturing neutron transport within homogeneous media.

Figure 5. Schematic diagram of the homogeneous medium rectangular basic unit.

3.1.2. Heterogeneous Pin-cell Unit

For the more complex pin-cell unit (*Figure 6*), characterized by a central fuel rod (radius = 0.475 cm) surrounded by moderator, a direct prediction using a single network proved challenging due to strong heterogeneity effects. The fuel region was defined by macroscopic cross-sections of $\Sigma_t = 0.50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Sigma_s = 0.32 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\nu\Sigma_f = 0.20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, while the moderator region had $\Sigma_t = 0.50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\Sigma_s = 0.49 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The decomposed prediction strategy (Section 2.3) was implemented via four specialized sub-networks: the first predicts the total outgoing scalar flux, the second determines its spatial distribution ratio across surfaces, the third resolves the angular distribution, and the fourth estimates the fission source term. Final angular flux values were reconstructed by combining these components. This architecture

delivered superior accuracy compared to a monolithic network, confirming its efficacy in managing strong heterogeneity. The final reconstructed angular flux predictions showed that 94.76% of samples had errors below 1.5%, while 99.86% of the fission source term errors were within 0.1%. These results confirm the model's high accuracy in handling strong spatial-angular coupling effects inherent in heterogeneous geometries.

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of pin-cell structure basic unit.

3.2. Fuel Assembly Problem

A 2D fuel assembly was constructed by combining fuel pin-cell units and pure moderator units (geometry shown in Figure 7). The eigenvalue converged to 1.02820 (Figure 8), deviating by only 59 pcm from the NECP-MCX reference (1.02879).

Figure 7. Schematic of the fuel assembly problem.

Figure 8. Eigenvalue convergence curve for the fuel assembly problem.

The spatial distributions also exhibited excellent agreement. The relative deviation of the neutron flux density distribution (Figure 9) was within $\pm 0.58\%$, and the fission source distribution error (Figure 10) was within $\pm 0.56\%$. These results validate the ability of the MC-DL-IC framework to not only converge

to the correct global eigenvalue but also to reconstruct high-fidelity local physics fields by combining localized neural surrogates.

Figure 9. Relative percentage deviation between predicted and reference neutron flux density distributions.

Figure 10. Relative percentage deviation between predicted and reference fission source distributions.

4. CONCLUSION AND PROSPECT

This study proposed a novel Monte Carlo-Deep Learning-Interface Current (MC-DL-IC) coupling method for neutron transport calculation. By integrating neural network surrogate models of standardized basic units within an iterative interface current framework, it enables accurate simulation of complex geometries using models trained solely on simple building blocks. Validation confirmed high accuracy, with eigenvalue errors below 100 pcm and relative errors in neutron flux density and fission source distributions within 1%.

The key innovation lies in a paradigm shift from problem-specific regression toward a physics-driven, combinatorial assembly of localized learning modules, effectively overcoming the generalization limitation of purely data-driven models. Future work will focus on: 1) Extending to multi-group energy structures to handle realistic spectra and resonance effects. The use of continuous-energy MC training data offers a potential pathway to bypass approximations in traditional cross-section generation. 2) Expanding the basic unit library (e.g., triangles, hexagons) to enhance geometric adaptability for modeling full cores. 3) Incorporating burnup and thermal-hydraulic feedback effects.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (1237050271).

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